

Educational Opportunities For Children In Need Of Development Assistance

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Abstract: *This article describes the scientific research work carried out on improving the educational system and content of children in need of special assistance, modernization, memory documents, a brief analysis of the educational opportunities of children with disabilities. Also, such issues as the specifics, legal framework, goals and objectives, needs and principles of children's educational technologies, in which scientists from foreign countries need special education, are covered.*

Keywords — Convention on the right of Children, "National Training Program", "Special Education necessity", inclusive education, inclusive education technology, curriculum, medium, method.

INTRODUCTION.

In any society, it is hoped that the young generation will grow up as mature and perfect people in all respects, grow up as worthy citizens and contribute to the development and prosperity of the state. According to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, which belongs to all children of the world, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", and a number of important regulatory documents such as the "National Personnel Training Program", all children, including children with disabilities in physical or mental development have the right to work, receive education, and find their place in life.

On December 1, 1993, 153 countries ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child, demonstrating their willingness to protect the future of children. The Convention is a United Nations treaty on children's rights worldwide. The Convention is the universal official code of rights of the child. In the convention, children's rights are divided into four categories, which include 54 articles.

In 1994, UNESCO prepared a document entitled "Necessity of special education", in which it considered the issues of organization and improvement of education for children and young people who need special education. In this type of education, the main place is devoted to the issues of rehabilitation.

The document states: "The purpose of organizing special education for people with special needs is to restore children and adolescents with disabilities in physical or mental development to society in independent living conditions like everyone else."

Y. L. Goncharova, O. S. Nikolskaya, O. I. Kukushkina stated that a child with special educational needs should have the necessary conditions for maximum development, education and training. It also states that it is necessary to carry out separate education for each category of children with disabilities according to each age, developmental

characteristics and stage of education in an equally clear, detailed and scientifically based manner.

Children with disabilities cannot perform tasks and tasks as quickly as children with normal development, but they can perform them at the level of ability. Disability does not mean incompetence.

In any situation, even in case of illness and deficiency, even if there are problems, the child continues to develop. D. B. Yakubzhanova said that the issue of education, upbringing and socialization of children with physical or mental developmental disabilities is widely researched by the scientific community. In accordance with the "Education for All" plan adopted on the basis of the Dakar Declaration, the issue of introducing inclusive education into the general education system throughout the world is gaining particular importance [9]. Today, the growing importance of the social approach to the concept of "disability" strongly contrasts with the fact that this category of individuals is not only a separate, inactive category of society that needs the help of others, but not only their defects from the first stages of their development, but also others. It is recognized that it is necessary to study the possibilities of active integration into society and socialization, to help him grow to the level of a person capable of meeting his needs in various fields through correctional-pedagogical technologies and methods.

The emergence and improvement of social experience in children with disabilities is more complicated than in children with normal development. Because physical and mental disabilities make it possible for them to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in various spheres of life in proportion to their age, and to be able to freely enter into social and cultural relations.

It is necessary to create the necessary psychological-pedagogical and correctional conditions for the education of children and adolescents with disabilities in an educational institution, to implement general education programs focused on their abilities, and to implement correctional works for their mental development and social adjustment.

In the world, it is recognized that children with disabilities in physical or mental development are equal participants in the development of society and the state in the political, economic, social, and cultural spheres.

To enable children with special educational needs to receive pre-school education, general secondary education, to strengthen their social protection system, to protect the rights of children with disabilities, and to involve them in inclusive education. Supported by UNICEF [2]. Despite the fact that the child has a disability, it is necessary to teach him the type of work he can do, educate him and help him find his place in society (social rehabilitation) [8].

In our country, favorable conditions are being created for the education and upbringing of children with disabilities and their adaptation to social life. In order to integrate them into the society, first of all, in order to restore their health as much as possible, work is being carried out on the basis of the "General education project for children with disabilities". This mainly involves the use of inclusive education opportunities.

As a result, it is becoming an urgent scientific problem to study the pedagogical-psychological features and unique possibilities of organizing inclusive education in depth, to identify the problems related to it, and to justify aspects of its effectiveness. Because the inclusive education method creates a convenient opportunity to ensure full participation of all children in the educational process, regardless of their mental and physical condition.

In particular, it is necessary for children with special needs to communicate with others, to grow up to be able to meet the demands of the social environment, to acquire the skills to meet their daily and household needs, to adapt to life and to be healthy in general education schools. You create facilities for him to be able to study under equal conditions with his peers, to enter into a friendly relationship with them, to master lessons on time, to approach assignments responsibly.

Inclusive education is not only among children with disabilities, but also among children raised in families based on a healthy lifestyle, in pre-school educational institutions, schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges. can create convenient opportunities for students. Through it, students can have a positive effect on each other, which will bring a good result. But sometimes the difference between healthy children and disabled children is noticed, the disabled child does not join his peers, hesitates, is ashamed and humiliated because he cannot use his opportunities, and some of them are raised too masculine in the family. It is observed that he acts stubbornly and capriciously, and in such conditions, it is necessary to make changes in the organization of educational practices and educational services.

All this makes it clear that the process of inclusive education has its own complexities and imposes serious requirements and responsibilities on teachers, class leaders, educators, and masters of professional skills working in this field. Based on the conducted researches and studies, inclusive education technology can be defined as follows: "Inclusive education technology (ITT) is a systematic, individualized,

situational, kind approach to children and youth with special needs in the continuous education system. It is a process in which pedagogical and psychological aspects of education are carried out according to modern requirements with the help of changing, special educational programs, materials, tools and methods.

As a result of the introduction of inclusive education in educational institutions from family to school, comprehensive schools, vocational colleges and higher educational institutions, it became known that the general attitude towards people with disabilities is changing. And this can serve as a factor for their success in life.

An inclusive education strategy developed for people with disabilities and introduced to society on a planned basis ensures continuity and continuity of education. Family - Kindergarten - School - Vocational College - Employment - this system will create a foundation for future parents to bring their children with disabilities to general education institutions and higher education institutions without risk.

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